

**e-InfraNet:
Emerging Visions for the Future
Development of Cloud Computing**

*European Network for co-ordination
of policies and programmes
on e-infrastructures (e-InfraNet)*

Version History

Version	Date	Changed pages / reason	Modified by
0.01	09.Feb.2012	First draft	MD
0.02	21 Mar 2012	Expansion of first draft	MD
0.03	4 Apr 2012	Inclusion of comments from Partners	MD
0.04	10 Apr 2012	Inclusion of diagrams	PLSS
0.05	15 Apr 2012	Conclusions	MB
0.9	5 May 2012	Final draft	MD
1.0	10 May 2012	Edit	PLSS
1.01	16 May 2012	Proof edit	PLSS

Acknowledgements

This report has been developed within the project “European Network for co-ordination of policies and programmes on e-infrastructures” (e-InfraNet.eu). The project is an ERA-NET co-funded by the 7th Framework Programme of the European Commission.

The consortium of the project is presented in the table below:

Participant organisation name	Short Name	Country
Higher Education Authority	HEA	IE
Higher Education Funding Council for England	HEFCE (JISC)	UK
SURFfoundation	SURF	NL
Foundation for Science and Technology	FCT	PT
Latvian Academy of Sciences	LAS	LV
Ministry of Economy and Competitiveness	MINECO	ES
CSC - IT Center for Science	CSC	FI
National Information Infrastructure Development Institute	NIIFI	HU
The Scientific and Technological Research Council of Turkey	TUBITAK	TR
The Israel-Europe R&D Directorate	ISERD	IL
The General Secretariat for Research and Technology	GSRT	GR
Department of Economy, Science and Innovation, Flemish Government	EWI	BE

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<i>Author(s):</i>	Matthew Dovey (JISC), Magchiel Bijsterbosch (SURF), Paul Stokes (JISC)
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Executive Summary

The technologies underlying “Cloud Computing” are not new, but cloud services and cloud technologies have the potential to offer new opportunities to researchers in terms of:

- new areas of computer scientific and sociological study into distributed computing
- new delivery mechanisms for research institutes to provide access to their compute and data resources
- new procurement mechanisms for research institutes to purchase compute and data resources
- new opportunities to undertake research without up-front capital expenditure or new opportunities for research collaborations

To benefit, the academic community needs an environment which allows for informed and effective negotiation between cloud consumers and providers. Obstacles to be negotiated include:

- legal and technical obstacles preventing migration between cloud providers
- the use of multiple cloud providers
- recognition of the limitations of cloud
- data retention by cloud providers

This would permit a free market for cloud. There are also key policy issues which will need to be solved to achieve such a free, risk free market allowing manual movement between clouds:

- shared procurement and negotiation
- advisory on cloud Service Level Agreements, licensing, legal issues and privacy
- portability between clouds
- interoperability between clouds
- cloud security and trust
- cultural changes

Various initiatives already exist which are addressing some of these issues. However alignment is needed between those initiatives to prevent unnecessary and divergent developments. Such an alignment would provide an overarching policy and governance framework to support these activities and enable cross-fertilisation between existing activities. These activities should furthermore be directed to:

- undertake procurement and national license negotiation between cloud service providers and academia
- provide template agreements between cloud service providers and academia
- assist academic run cloud services as regards agreements and service levels
- advocate standards and legal frameworks into the EU
- benchmark cloud providers as regards trust, reliability, privacy etc.

For the coordination of national bodies governing these aspects, the NREN model for network provision may provide a suitable architecture to base this upon. The coordination bodies and communities can also serve as centres of expertise. In addition, overarching coordination at the EU and global levels could provide a necessary policy framework for delivering the federated cloud vision.

A next step would be to instigate the formation of a broadly formulated think tank to investigate the policy structures outlined above.

1 Introduction

This document is a policy paper from the e-InfraNet partners concerning the impact of the use of cloud computing—“Cloud”—on e-infrastructures for science and research across the European Research Area (ERA). The document has been produced in response to a request from the European Commission for advice and guidance on this topic. This paper will focus on definitions, how the guidance was formulated, the major issues surrounding the use of Cloud (focussing on its use in academic circles) and present a series of conclusions relating to the essential components for cloud adoption in the academic sector.

1.1 Origins of Cloud

“Cloud computing” has emerged in recent years as a term to describe a wide variety of online services and service provision realising a vision of John McCarthy from the 1960s that “computation may someday be organised as a public utility.” Many of the modern-day characteristics of cloud computing—elastic provision, provided as a utility, online, illusion of infinite supply—the comparison to the electricity industry and the use of public, private, government, and community forms, were thoroughly explored in Douglas Parkhill’s 1966 book, ‘The Challenge of the Computer Utility’.

The wide variety of uses of the term “Cloud Computing” (not least those employed by marketers) can cause confusion.

However, most clouds combine elements of:

- Self-service
- Delivery as a service
- Consumption based pricing
- Standard connectivity
- Multi-tenancy
- Elasticity

There are now more rigorous definitions of cloud computing, the most commonly accepted being from NIST (see inset) which in the Cloud Computing Technology Roadmap defines cloud in terms of service models and deployment models.¹

A Definition of Cloud Computing*

Cloud computing is a model for enabling ubiquitous, convenient, on-demand network access to a shared pool of configurable computing resources (e.g., networks, servers, storage, applications, and services) that can be rapidly provisioned and released with minimal management effort or service provider interaction. This cloud model is composed of five essential characteristics, three service models, and four deployment models.

Essential Characteristics:

- On-demand self-service
- Broad network access.
- Resource pooling
- Rapid elasticity
- Measured service

Service Models:

- Software as a Service (SaaS)
- Platform as a Service (PaaS)
- Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS)

Deployment Models:

- Private cloud
- Community cloud
- Public cloud
- Hybrid cloud

*Derived from “The NIST Definition of Cloud Computing”.
<http://csrc.nist.gov/publications/nistpubs/800-145/SP800-145.pdf>

¹ http://www.nist.gov/itl/cloud/upload/SP_500_293_volumell.pdf

From a research perspective, cloud offers a number of potential advantages:

- New areas of computer scientific and sociological study into distributed computing
- New delivery mechanisms for research institutes to provide access to their compute and data resources
- New procurement mechanisms for research institutes to purchase compute and data resources
- New opportunities to undertake research without up-front capital expenditure or new opportunities for research collaborations

1.2 e-InfraNet Workshop

Fifty seven participants from eighteen countries attended the e-InfraNet Cloud Computing workshop on the 29th and 30th of March 2011, in Leuven, Belgium, organised by the Joint Information Systems Committee in the UK (JISC) under the auspices of the e-InfraNet project.

This workshop was the second in a series of workshops focussing on each of the topic areas identified in the e-InfraNet description of work—Green ICT, Cloud Computing and Openness. The objectives of the e-InfraNet workshops are to gather further inputs from partners and external participants on these three areas around which e-InfraNet will build joint activities and, ultimately, propose policy advice and recommendations to the European Commission.

This first workshop on Cloud Computing offered the e-InfraNet partners a thorough overview of some of the key themes, questions, issues and challenges relating to the role and impact of cloud computing on e-infrastructures for science and research. The workshop was organized around a series of presentations from experts in the field of cloud computing, discussion sessions in four breakout groups and round table plenary discussions. Presentations were delivered by experts on the following topics:

- Cloud computing market solutions
- Why invest in Cloud Computing?
- Is Cloud Computing beneficial to research?
- Using Cloud for research
- The SARA HPC Cloud
- What is the impact of Cloud Computing on existing research infrastructures?
- Will grids evolve into cloud computing provision?

This policy paper is based on conclusions² from that workshop and other cloud related activities.

² http://e-infranet.eu/wp-content/uploads/2011/07/D1-2-3-Proceedings-of-the-e-InfraNet-Cloud-Computing-Workshop-Leuven-29-30-march_FINAL.pdf

THE CLOUD THINGY

Cartoon credit: [geek and poke](#)

2 Core concepts

Traditionally IT has involved high up front capital costs—either in purchasing hardware and/or software licensing. The cloud model offers a paradigm shift in moving towards a recurrent fee based on the actual usage of services, rather than a capital cost based on estimated peak usage. This offers consumers the advantage of being able to scale up and scale down usage as determined by circumstances. From an organisational perspective, the utilisation of capacity problem is transferred to the provider. At the same time the business model—that of providing pay-per-use subscription based services rather than single purchase products—offers providers a recurrent and possibly more constant revenue stream. One that is no longer driven by having to consistently offer new “must-have” features to persuade consumers to abandon existing versions of software and hardware and move to new versions of the same software and hardware.

2.1 Cloud Terms and Definitions

The term “cloud computing” has emerged organically to describe a broad variety of IT infrastructure and software provision. The term has been further complicated by its adoption as a marketing brand by many suppliers. This complicates discussion of strategies and policies for “cloud” since participants in developing these often have different concepts behind their understanding of cloud.

The key motivations behind Cloud are those of self-service and ubiquitous access to services:

- **Self-service**—a potential customer can use a new cloud service with minimal upfront cost either in time or effort, or in financial cost. This is typically achieved by simplified interfaces either user interfaces or programmatic interfaces dependent on the service being offered.
- **Ubiquitous access to services**—the oft quoted vision of the cloud is that you can access the same services independent of device or location. This is achieved by offering online services for tasks typically associated as being carried out on local devices such as computation, storage and software.

From an organisational business perspective, cloud offers the opportunity to procure commercial off the shelf (**COTS**) products that are delivered ‘as a service’. Depending upon the category of service, the delivery model of cloud services makes some existing IT-related business functions redundant, in particular those related to IT service and application management. However, the process of procuring cloud services to replace ubiquitous IT operations that were otherwise provided by the central IT department and/or data centre has many of the classic outsourcing characteristics and issues—governance, quality of service, security, maintaining innovation capabilities for instance—associated with it.

Cloud services are typically divided into three distinct categories (or service models, using the NIST definitions of cloud³) depending on the type of service offered and the target audience (Figure 1—Cloud stack model):

- **Software as a Service (SaaS)**—Offering software (for example word processing, e-mail and financial tools) as an **online** service instead of locally installed software. This covers a range of

³ http://www.nist.gov/itl/cloud/upload/SP_500_293_volumell.pdf

scales from small personal tools (such as managing photos) to large organisational tools (financial systems, customer relations management, etc.).

- **Platform as a Service (PaaS)**—Offering enterprise middleware components such as messaging systems or workflow engines as an online service (examples include Yahoo pipes, Microsoft Azure, and the like).
- **Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS)**—Providing storage and computer processing

Figure 1—Cloud stack model

as online services. Computer processing is either offered as a virtual machine—the service functions as if it were a real computer but with dynamically allocated memory/processor—such as Amazon compute cloud, or as a service that requires developing software to the platform—Hadoop, Google compute. Storage is either offered as a virtual disk (as with Amazon S3) or a structure store (for instance a cloud database).

Software as a Service is typically targeted at end consumers, whilst Platform as a Service and Infrastructure as a Service are targeted at infrastructure providers (either offering external services, or internal services to an organisation). It is important to distinguish between these when discussing cloud, as comparisons between these different types are not always valid.

An emergent area within Infrastructure as a Service which is particularly relevant to research has been discussion of **HPC⁴ as a Service (HPCaaS)**. From a technological standpoint, whilst cloud is feasible at the small scale for some HPC type computing problems⁵, at the larger scale HPC is still better supplied as dedicated hardware. Few virtualisation engines support the number of processors or the amount of memory typically associated with HPC facilities. In addition, virtualisation engines introduce additional overheads particularly in terms of latency. Delivery of HPC using cloud IaaS is not feasible due to the high latencies⁶ introduced. However, IaaS does offer new insights into business and access models for HPC resources particularly as regards providing access to HPC for commercial users, and accordingly providers specialized on are HPC starting to appear⁷.

It is also important to recognise that a particular cloud service will be characterised by its intended consumer. The cloud service may be targeted at an individual (such as many SaaS cloud offerings in the social networking space), at organisations (as many IaaS cloud offering will be), or at virtual organisations or collaborations of organisations. However, the latter is currently hampered by existing licensing models that expect a single legal entity.

⁴ HPC—High Performance Computing. Typically used for computing problems consisting a large number of sequential calculations with interdependent inputs and outputs.

⁵ http://cisjournal.org/journalofcomputing/archive/vol3no2/vol3no2_20.pdf

⁶ The inherent delays within the system, especially apparent when passing data from one node to another.

⁷ <https://www.blackskycomputing.com/>

The term “Cloud” has also become common in describing some of the technologies which are typically used by cloud service. These include:

- Advanced browser technologies such as ajax, flash, silverlight and html5. These can offer rich functionality applications within the web browser which have similar features to their desktop equivalents but can be offered ubiquitously online as typically used by SaaS providers.
- Compartmentalised, task specific, web based programmatic interfaces are often utilised by PaaS providers to simplify integration of their services with other external and internal services.
- Virtualisation technologies such as VMWare, Xen, and Hyper-V are used by IaaS providers to enable them to provide a service typically associated with physical hardware on an on demand and ubiquitous access basis.

In order to distinguish between discussions of “cloud” when applied to service provision as opposed to the underlying technological development which has allowed cloud services to become a practical offering, this paper will refer to the former as “cloud services” and the latter as “cloud technologies”.

Figure 2—Cloud deployments

Cloud technologies have been deployed within particular organisations in order to reduce costs, increase flexibility or to offer easier to use services⁸. These cloud deployments—accessible only by members of

⁸ The NIST Cloud Computing Technology Roadmap refers to these as deployment models. http://www.nist.gov/itl/cloud/upload/SP_500_293_volumell.pdf

that organisation—are often referred to as “**private clouds**”. In contrast, “**public clouds**” refer to external cloud service providers accessible to all.

In some cases cloud technologies have been used by a consortium of organisations in order to offer combined services as a cost effective alternative to providing the same service internally (also known as shared services). These deployments are often referred to as “**community clouds**” or “**sector clouds**”. In many respects, these community clouds are similar to the concept of “virtual organisations” as used in the grid community. Finally, there is a model whereby services are offered internally on a private cloud but at peak demands public clouds are used to meet the extra demand. These are often termed “**hybrid clouds**” (with the use of public clouds to meet demand referred to as “**cloud bursting**”). The inverse setup—publicly located clouds with connections through to private clouds for certain functions—may also be employed when security issues (for example the processing of privacy sensitive data) prevent the use of public cloud services throughout. In this scenario public clouds are used to support certain functions (such as document management) and trusted (on-premise) environments are used to cater for specific applications. Figure 2—Cloud deployments (above) illustrates these different deployment types.

Another increasingly common application of “hybrid clouds” is to use the public cloud as an additional resource for backup, resilience or disaster recovery.

2.2 Commonly Held Beliefs About Cloud Computing

There are a number of claims made about cloud computing which to date have not been justified by experience:

“Cloud Computing is the future of all computing”

As with many advances in technology, there is a tendency of hyperbole in expectations surrounding their application (as shown by for instance the Gartner Hype Cycle⁹). Cloud is no different in that it has been put forward as the future of all computing. In reality cloud is an evolutionary application of technology and approaches (and in particular business models) which have been under development for a long time. “Cloud” has been useful in raising awareness, credence and applicability of the associated cloud technologies in production systems.

It is true to say that cloud has applications in many areas. However, it is not always appropriate to use cloud in all circumstances. Cloud services are highly dependent on network infrastructure. This can limit their application where there is poor network infrastructure (as can often be the case particularly with mobile networks) or where very high bandwidth networks are required, for example in research problems dealing with “big data”. Also, some research problems require highly specialised computer infrastructure which is unlikely to be available from commercial cloud providers who will, in the main, be driven by market forces to deliver generic services which will appeal to a broader audience. However, research computing providers such as HPC providers may adopt elements of the cloud service provisioning model—such as the payments model—whilst at the same time maintaining support for more bespoke research applications. The e-InfraNet Cloud workshop concluded that cloud was particularly effective in “embarrassingly parallel” computations. In other words, computations where a task can be subdivided into completely independent subtasks¹⁰. Many research problems, however, consist of subtasks which are highly dependent on each other. These require specialised low latency computing infrastructures such as HPC.

In general, commercial cloud providers will be economically driven towards providing generic services with wide and ubiquitous applicability. Whilst there may be more specialised services within community clouds, there will always be the need for bespoke, highly specialised services which may not be delivered as cloud services (although may in certain circumstances be delivered via cloud technologies or on private clouds). It should also be noted that cloud marks a trend towards centralisation of computing infrastructure. Such trends in both technical structures and organisational structures are often followed by a reactive trend towards decentralisation.

“Cloud Computing is cheaper than internal provision”

The economics of cloud computing is driven by scale. A cloud service provider can offer lower running costs than a smaller provider with more modest requirements due to the scale of its data centre. However, a public cloud service provider also needs to have a business model that ensures a profit margin taking into account fluctuating demand and income. Taking these margins into account, an organisation with large computing requirements which can achieve economies of scale may financially be better off with internal provision (although may benefit from a private cloud or the use of cloud technologies). A recent report from the US Department of Energy indicated that the use of a public cloud could be thirteen

⁹ <http://www.gartner.com/technology/research/methodologies/hype-cycle.jsp>

¹⁰ Examples include: <http://cloudresearch.jiscinvolve.org/wp/category/projects/flood-modelling-for-cities/>
<http://cloudresearch.jiscinvolve.org/wp/category/projects/clouds-in-space/>

times the cost of internal provision given their scale of operation¹¹. A study commissioned by EPSRC and JISC in the UK has shown that cloud instances suitable for scientific application can be around 1.5 times more expensive than a well-utilised institutional cluster.¹²

As mentioned above a cloud service provider needs to accommodate variable demand, so will typically need additional physical resources beyond that in use to accommodate growth so that consumers can expand their cloud capability “instantly”. The cloud service provider has to absorb this additional unused capacity into their charging model. At present, as cloud is a growth industry, these costs are low and can be absorbed into the operating budget. However, when cloud services reach saturation, we may see a rapid increase in the cost of cloud services.

Another aspect of the economics of cloud which is often overlooked—particularly in relation to migrating services to the cloud—is the existing embedded cost connected to a service in terms of current infrastructure, migration and skills. In addition the cloud migration exercise may expose hidden costs—activities which are not normally exposed in financial terms but nevertheless occur taking up resources. These overlooked expenses are financially costed into the cloud service.

On the other hand, when using the cloud, organisations can budget their computing resources as opex¹³ rather than capex¹⁴ transactions; they pay and access what they actually need and use, which can change dynamically with demand.

In addition to the pure cost aspect, cloud services (or outsourced services in general) may provide a higher quality of service compared to small scale in-house activities. As such, although more expensive in its absolute sense, a cloud solution may still be beneficial economically taking into account the quality aspects.

The real benefit of cloud is its flexibility (or elasticity) particularly where demand is uncertain or unpredictable. In general cloud is particularly suited to cost-efficient small scale or piloting new services within an organisation. This is of particular benefit in the research space in that it allows experiments to be carried out without major up front capital expenditure.

“Cloud computing is Secure”

Cloud services are sometimes considered “secure” in the sense that they outsource requirements such as backup or have multiple sites in case of failure. Nonetheless, there are concerns about how secure cloud services are for sensitive information.

A recent study by the Ponemon Institute¹⁵ on the security of cloud computing providers uncovered some disturbing attitudes relating to security in the cloud. The majority of cloud computing providers surveyed did not believe their organization viewed the security of their cloud services as a competitive advantage. Furthermore, they did not consider cloud computing security as one of their most important responsibilities and did not believe their products or services substantially protected and secured the confidential or sensitive information of their customers. They believed it was their customer’s responsibility to secure the cloud and not their responsibility. They also said their systems and applications are not always evaluated for security threats prior to deployment to customers. On average

¹¹ http://science.energy.gov/~media/ascr/pdf/program-documents/docs/Magellan_Final_Report.pdf

¹² http://www.jisc.ac.uk/media/documents/programmes/research_infrastructure/costcloudresearch.pdf, p. 28.

¹³ opex—operational expenditure

¹⁴ capex—capital expenditure

¹⁵ Security of Cloud Computing Providers Study. <http://www.ca.com/~media/Files/IndustryResearch/security-of-cloud-computing-providers-final-april-2011.pdf>

providers of cloud computing technologies allocated 10% or less of their operational resources to security and most did not have confidence that customers' security requirements were being met. Cloud providers in the study said the primary reasons why customers purchase cloud resources were lower cost and faster deployment of applications. In contrast, improved security or compliance with regulations was viewed as an unlikely reason for choosing cloud services. The majority of cloud providers in the study admitted they did not have dedicated security personnel to oversee the security of cloud applications, infrastructure or platforms. Providers of private cloud resources appeared to attach more importance and have a higher level of confidence in their organization's ability to meet security objectives than providers of public and hybrid cloud solutions. Whilst security as a "true" service from the cloud is rarely offered to customers today, about one-third of the cloud providers in the study were considering such solutions as a new source of revenue sometime in the next two years.

In addition, as outlined below, there are issues over legislative frameworks as to when government agencies may demand access to data, and relating to the guaranteed deletion of data from cloud services after a contract is terminated.

2.3 Cloud Federation

Cloud Federation, also termed Intercloud, is a vision of an interconnected global "cloud of clouds"¹⁶. This differs from most current hybrid cloud deployment in that these typically consist of very tightly coupled private and public clouds. Most developments towards Cloud Federations and Intercloud share an ultimate vision of transparent dynamic management and automatic scaling between different cloud services and cloud providers.

Figure 3—Cloud Federation

This vision poses a number of very difficult technical questions and demands. Historically, previous attempts to automate scaling and dynamic provision such as CORBA, Web Services and Grid have failed to achieve this on a global cross-enterprise level, although have been effective within the enterprise. It is therefore a genuine possibility that such approaches will only gain traction within private and community clouds. As the US Energy Department observes, the cloud technology stack is still relatively immature

¹⁶ InterCloud: Utility-Oriented Federation of Cloud Computing Environments for Scaling of Application Services—Rajkumar Buyya^{1,2}, Rajiv Ranjan³, and Rodrigo N. Calheiros¹

even without the complexities of Cloud Federation¹⁷. However, there are activities to develop Cloud Federations within Community Clouds, through activities such as SIENA, EGI Cloud Federation Taskforce and the CERN/ESA Cloud Initiative (outlined below). Figure 4—Cloud model evolution—shows how the cloud model is progressing in this context. Anecdotally it would appear that current provision lies (on the whole) between stage 2 and stage 3. The EU is already supporting work towards this Cloud Federation vision within Community Clouds with the potential to extend to cross- enterprise.

Alongside this work towards the longer term vision, it is also essential to encourage an environment which:

- allows for informed and effective negotiation between cloud consumers and providers,
- removes legal and technical obstacles preventing migration between cloud providers or the use of multiple cloud providers, and
- prevents unnecessary obstacles to the uptake of cloud whilst recognising the real limitations of cloud.

These would permit a free market for cloud applications in the short term, which would allow consumers to move transparently between different cloud providers without risk of being locked into a particular provider, and provide assurance that no data resides with a previous provider. In the long term this would provide an essential policy foundation for the on-going developments towards the Global Federated Cloud vision.

Section 3 outlines a number of areas where action relating to the academic sector's use of cloud is needed.

¹⁷ http://science.energy.gov/~media/ascr/pdf/program-documents/docs/Magellan_Final_Report.pdf

2.4 Overview of Current EU Actions

2.4.1 SIENA

SIENA, the Standards and Interoperability for e-Infrastructure Implementation Initiative (2010-2012)¹⁸, is a Support Action (CSA-SA of the INFRA-2010-3.3: Coordination Actions, conferences and studies supporting policy development, including international cooperation for e-Infrastructures). The main strategic objective of SIENA is to accelerate and co-ordinate the adoption and evolution of interoperable Distributed Computing Infrastructures (DCI) through engagement with other Standard Development Organisations (SDO) and major stakeholders to forge community agreements on best practices and standards for distributed computing.

SIENA contributes to a future e-infrastructures roadmap¹⁹ which focuses on interoperability and standards. This is undertaken by working with DCI projects and SDOs to gain an in-depth understanding of how distributed computing technology is being developed in this context. The roadmap defines scenarios, identifies trends, investigates the innovation and impact sparked by cloud and grid computing, and delivers insight into how standards & the policy framework are defining and shaping current and future development and deployment in Europe and globally.

2.4.2 EGI Cloud Federation TaskForce

The European Grid Initiative (EGI)²⁰ is a federation of national and domain specific resource infrastructure providers made up of individual resource centres. Many of these resource centres have been experimenting with the deployment of virtualised management environments to improve the local delivery of services. In addition, many of EGI's current and new user communities would like to access the flexibility provided by virtualisation across the infrastructure on demand in a 'cloud like' environment. Federating these individual virtualised resources is a major priority for EGI. This initiative has started with the EGI User Virtualisation Workshop, and the drafting of the EGI Cloud Integration Profile.

The EGI Cloud Federation Taskforce²¹ is developing a Community Cloud for the EGI by:

- writing a blueprint document for EGI Resource Providers that wish to securely federate and share their virtualised environments as part of the EGI production infrastructure;
- deploying a test bed to evaluate the integration of virtualised resources within the existing EGI production infrastructure for monitoring, accounting and information services;
- investigating and cataloguing the requirements for community facing services based on or deployed through virtualised resources;
- providing feedback to relevant technology providers on their implementations and any changes needed for deployment into the production infrastructure;
- identifying and working with user communities willing to be early adopters of the test bed infrastructure to help prioritise its future development;
- identifying issues that need to be addressed by other areas of EGI (for example policy, operations, support & dissemination).

¹⁸ <http://www.sienainitiative.eu>

¹⁹ http://www.sienainitiative.eu/Pages/Static.aspx?id_documento=77e47efb-7b89-4b20-aa1b-ea1a60ef5c08

²⁰ <http://www.egi.eu>

²¹ <https://wiki.egi.eu/wiki/Fedcloud-tf:FederatedCloudsTaskForce>

2.4.3 Helix Nebula

Helix Nebula is a Community Cloud consisting of a consortium of leading IT providers—listed below—along with the Cloud Security Alliance, the OpenNebula Project, the European Grid Infrastructure and three of Europe’s biggest research centres (CERN1, EMBL2 and ESA3). The IT providers involved include:

- Atos,
- Capgemini,
- CloudSigma,
- Interoute,
- Logica,
- Orange Business Services,
- SAP,
- SixSq,
- Telefonica,
- Terradue,
- Thales,
- The Server Labs, and T-Systems

It will support the massive IT requirements of European scientists, and become available to governmental organisations and industry after an initial pilot phase.

During a two-year pilot phase, Helix Nebula will be deployed and tested based on three flagship projects proposed by CERN, EMBL and ESA designed to:

- accelerate the search for the elusive Higgs particle
- boost large-scale genomic analyses in biomedical research
- support research into natural disasters

3 Essential Components for Cloud Adoption in the Academic Sector

Cloud service and technologies are of interest to the academic sector in that they can offer:

- new areas of computer scientific and sociological study into distributed computing
- new delivery mechanisms for research institutes to provide access to their compute and data resources
- new procurement mechanisms for research institutes to purchase compute and data resources
- new opportunities to undertake research without up-front capital expenditure or new opportunities for research collaborations

Many research tools can be offered via cloud services and technologies including:

- research data acquisition (e.g. shared e-labs)
- data processing (including specialised hardware such as HPC and GPU clusters)
- data presentation (e.g. simulation tools); research publication (e.g. open access)
- researcher collaboration platforms (e.g. Google apps, SURFConext)
- research outputs repositories and archives

However, for cloud adoption to be truly beneficial to the Academic Sector, it is essential to encourage an environment which:

- allows for informed and effective negotiation between cloud consumers and providers
- removes legal and technical obstacles preventing migration between cloud providers or the use of multiple cloud providers, and
- prevents unnecessary obstacles to the uptake of cloud whilst recognising the real limitations of cloud.

This would permit a free market for cloud applications in the short term, which would allow consumers to move transparently between different cloud providers without risk of being locked into a particular provider, whilst at the same time being assured that no data remains with a previous provider. In the long term this would provide an essential policy foundation for the on-going developments towards the Global Federated Cloud vision.

This section outlines some of the issues which need to be tackled within the Academic sector. Unfortunately, the ubiquity of the cloud is not matched by a general and standardized collaborative capacity. Concepts such as virtual organizations or support for more casual and short term research collaborations do not currently form part of the cloud stack and their omission acts as a barrier for collaborative research. The following sections address obstacles to achieving the desired functionality. Namely to share data, services, and resources between researchers using different cloud providers.

3.1 Shared procurement and negotiation

National negotiation and procurement services have been effective in the Higher Education sector in securing cost effective deals for networking, software and digital content. The e-InfraNet partners believe that it is likely that a similar model would be effective within member states for negotiating cloud services. There are a number of different models which would need to be investigated:

- A centralised procurement model, whereby long term commitments to cloud services are purchased nationally and then sold to individual organisations, consortia, communities or end

users. This would be analogous to the NREN model for network provision. However, this model is contrary to the dynamic, on demand flexibility which motivates the use of cloud services.

- A centralised negotiation model whereby academic discounts are negotiated nationally, but individual organisations, consortia, communities and end users purchase on an on-demand basis with the cloud service providers. This would be analogous to most academic software and content licensing discounts. This model is already followed by SURFmarket in the Netherlands and the JISC University Modernisation Fund Shared IT Infrastructure programme²² in the UK.

In addition, there is a need to investigate whether such models would scale to an intra-national level—for example to support trans-border collaborations—and how national procurement services could collaborate and share good practice internationally.

3.2 Advisory on cloud Service Level Agreements, licensing, legal issues and privacy

In addition to cost negotiation between cloud consumers and cloud service providers, the workshop also identified the need for advice at both national and trans-national levels over the licensing, service level agreements and legal issues to cloud consumers. Whilst these would be appreciated by organisations when negotiating contracts with cloud providers, the self-service model of cloud services would mean that it will increasingly be the case that the end researcher will be directly involved in the procurement process. Guidance and model templates could cover:

- Privacy and security issues
- Resilience and reliability expectations
- Backup and retention policy—not all cloud services offer backup facilities. In addition, it is important to know in advance what the cloud service provider policy is as regards ensuring the deletion of data in particular when migrating from one provider to another.
- Intellectual Property (IP) ownership—some cloud services for both data and compute will claim a level of ownership or reserve rights to the data which the end user may not be comfortable with, or may be subject to local legislation such as the US Patriot Act²³

Similar guidance to both academic institutions and communities also wishing to avail themselves of (or indeed be providers of) cloud services would also be required.

At a global level there is still confusion over the legislative domain which applies to a cloud service where the organisation providing the cloud service, the hardware providing the cloud services and the area to which cloud services are offered may all be in different territories. These cannot be legislated for at either national or European levels, but global case law is gradually emerging²⁴. Advice on the evolving law and emergent frameworks is important, as is providing advocacy from (and feedback to) the academic sector regarding legal developments. Researchers need to be able to feel confident that providers are adhering to such frameworks, and this could be achieved via mechanisms for certifying providers against such frameworks and standards.

²² <http://www.jisc.ac.uk/whatwedo/programmes/umf.aspx>

²³ <http://www.zdnet.com/blog/igeneration/case-study-how-the-usa-patriot-act-can-be-used-to-access-eu-data/8805>

²⁴ Examples include <http://www.technolog.msnbc.msn.com/technology/technolog/megaupload-founders-homes-raided-5m-luxury-cars-seized-84897> and <http://torrentfreak.com/us-resume-file-sharing-domain-seizures-110201/>

Ironically, many current licensing models for cloud assume that the customer is either an individual or a single organisation, and raise barriers when the cloud service is intended for use by a consortium or virtual organisation which crosses multiple organisations. This can be addressed if community clouds form a distinct legal entity for their collaboration, for example using legal instruments such as the European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC) framework²⁵ as used by many ESFRI projects²⁶. However, such legal frameworks may be too heavy weight for more casual or short term research collaborations. Also many software applications and software libraries used by research projects have licenses which assume that the software will be installed on local dedicated hardware. They do not permit use on virtual external cloud services, particularly when these are in use by multiple institutions. Similar problems were encountered running such applications on grid services. There is the need for joint negotiation to provide pressure on software providers to allow for “cloud-friendly” licenses.

3.3 Portability between clouds

Portability between clouds is a key essential to provide a free market, in order to allow ease of migration between different cloud providers. The barriers are both technical and policy based.

The NIST Cloud Standards Roadmap²⁷ identifies three key areas of technical standardisation for clouds:

- Security
- Interoperability
- Portability

Portability is one of the more underdeveloped areas in cloud computing, with the main key standard being the ‘Open Virtualisation Format’ for virtual machines which allows virtual hardware to be migrated between different providers. Yet this is really only applicable to Platform as a Service base cloud services offering virtual hardware services. However, since the publication of the current version of NIST Standards Roadmap, OASIS²⁸ has formed a technical committee developing a standard for Topology and Orchestration Specification for Cloud Applications (TOSCA)²⁹ which permits the portability of more complex cloud applications.

Standardisation alone is not sufficient in this area. Although there is an already well-established format for migration of Platform as a Service virtual hardware between providers, few such cloud service providers support this in their customer facing interfaces even when the technology is supported by their underlying systems. The ability, facility and right to migrate needs to be in the service level agreements enabling application migration both into and out of the cloud service provider.

Another key aspect of portability is that of data portability. The NIST Cloud Standard roadmap observes that *“Data portability is more complex and more fundamental to the notion of portability. It puts the ultimate control over data in the hands of the owner of that data, not the Web application that uses it or the service provider that hosts the application. Cloud consumers need to maintain control of their data. Moving data from one cloud provider to another includes the need to securely delete the old storage space.”* The very different varieties and volume of data between different applications make data portability a complex area. However, outlining good practice for cloud service providers in terms of well

²⁵ http://ec.europa.eu/research/infrastructures/index_en.cfm?pg=eric

²⁶ http://ec.europa.eu/research/infrastructures/index_en.cfm?pg=esfri

²⁷ http://www.nist.gov/manuscript-publication-search.cfm?pub_id=909024

²⁸ OASIS (Organization for the Advancement of Structured Information Standards) - <http://www.oasis-open.org/>

²⁹ http://www.oasis-open.org/committees/tc_home.php?wg_abbrev=tosca

documented interfaces and interoperability should lower the cost of migration. It should be noted that the data porting process is not complete until the data is removed and/or erased from the old cloud provider. Sometimes called the “right to be forgotten,” the consumer’s ability to delete data and be assured that the data is completely erased, is as essential to a user’s control over that data as the ability to retrieve it. As well as technical issues, there are also legislative issues which may prevent this. There are both legal frameworks for enforcing deletion, and also other legal frameworks for data retention.

3.4 Interoperability between Clouds

Interoperability between clouds allows application on different clouds to communicate and share information. This ranges from identity management and the exchange of data between services to the ability to mutually use each other’s resources (virtual machines, virtual networks, virtual storage, etc.) by different clouds belonging to different administrative domains. The e-InfraNet Workshop identified a tension between cloud providers and cloud consumers over the issue of whether it was too early to standardise in this area. There is a danger that effort within standards bodies and academia will not make it into core products. At the moment many of the implementations of current standardisation efforts are either immature or peripheral to the core products. On the other hand, there is often wide scale adoption of proprietary standards if they exist. Collective procurement may help to have a critical mass to steer development of services, such as adherence to standards to allow for access federation such as Shibboleth or SAML 2.0 or content interoperability standards such as OpenSocial or CMIS. The US Department of Energy report into cloud computing also concluded that many of the more complex and standard based cloud stacks are still immature and lack resilience.

3.5 Cloud Security and Trust

Ultimately cloud services require trust between the cloud service provider and the consumer. This requires a mixture of legal, technical and social frameworks, and must include light touch, bottom-up approaches. The e-InfraNet Cloud workshop concluded that “Cloud also forced new models of trust in third party providers (as well as the legal and policy frameworks underpinning this trust)”. The Ponemon Study into Security of Cloud Providers referred to earlier suggests that this is not always regarded as important by current cloud providers. However, researchers need to be assured that their research is secure, particularly when that data is sensitive or contains personal information and there are additional legal obligations on the researcher. The researcher also needs to trust that the cloud service will work as advertised, so that any conclusions from analysis undertaken on the cloud are valid and not compromised by errors or inconsistencies introduced by the cloud service.

The International Working Group on Data Protection in Telecommunications have recognised this issue and have issued a memorandum outlining the need for best practice and guidance for risk assessment, audit trails and data handling³⁰. Within the research and education space, it needs to be investigated whether there is scope for national and even EU level benchmarking of cloud providers against emerging good practice and guidelines, as well as developing guidelines where gaps exist. This could be, for example, along the lines of the SURFmarket which, following centralised procurement through inclusion in a service catalogue, can provide some level of certification for cloud providers in terms of technical interoperability (for example SURFconext), reliability and resilience, data privacy and right to be forgotten, service levels, and so on.

³⁰ http://datenschutz-berlin.de/attachments/873/Sopot_Memorandum_Cloud_Computing.pdf

3.6 Cultural Changes

One of the conclusions from the e-InfraNet Cloud Workshop was that, traditionally, many research groups defined themselves by the resources that the group possessed, for example computation clusters, HPC facilities, grid facilities and the like. Their competitive advantage was based upon the computation capacity that they possessed in house. Cloud services democratise access to these resources offering new opportunities driven more by research innovation than hardware capacity. It forces new models on the research support team and the need for collaborative teams across many different support roles (tool development, algorithm development, system administration, etc.) as well as researchers. Community clouds may offer longer term career prospects to such support roles, in that they may provide support staff to move between short term projects and institutions as the demands require whilst still offering longer term prospects of employment and career development than temporary project limited positions.

The new purchasing models offer both flexibility and challenges. Whilst cloud services offer the ability to get around institutional limitations, they also make the end user more aware of often hidden costs. The workshop concluded that, in terms of purchasing, all the benefits of the cloud service model tended to fall on the budget holder rather than the end user, the researcher. Whilst the budget holder could ensure that costs were directly related to need, it was at the expense of the user having to change practice, adapt to new funding models, port software codes etc. Moving to cloud services would mean that the researchers would become more aware of the real costs involved in undertaking their research, and this might make them more conservative in their innovation and research aspirations (which is generally perceived as a negative factor in the research community). Researchers would need to be much more aware of the financial, ecological and societal impacts of their research. However, cloud was only one driver for this cultural change. Increasing pressures on the financial and ecological costs of research may have this result independently of cloud.

The pay as you go model of cloud services has led to hitherto unrealised obstacles being placed in the path of research projects relating to both institutional issues and funding agencies. Funding agencies may not recognise cloud services as a valid budgetary expense, or expect hardware and software costs to be born from capital expenditure at the beginning of the project rather than incurred throughout the project. At an institutional level, current procurement processes often do not support cloud service purchasing models. A recently funded project—which has been explicitly funded to investigate the use of cloud for research—had extreme difficulty in purchasing £20K of cloud services. The cloud service provided did not support invoicing, and expected to be paid by credit card. However, the relevant departmental credit card had a substantially lower limit. On application to the institutions finance department, it was initially suggested that the project use internal resources or use the money to buy dedicated servers, despite this undermining the entire purpose of the project. The finance department then asked for an EU-wide tendering process—their procedures required such a process for procurement activities over a certain level. This also would not have worked since the self-service model of cloud services does not accommodate service provider bidding to provide services. Ultimately this provider selection hurdle was overcome through the acceptance of a cost comparison of various providers. It was then suggested that the principle investigator use their own personal credit card and “claim it back”, but the institution also refused to guarantee that they would reimburse the cost. In the end, the institution only permitted the purchase of cloud services when the principle investigator threatened to return the project funding to the funding agency.

4 Conclusion

Cloud computing integrates different developments within the technical, economic, cultural and governance realms which are not necessarily new individually, but when combined provide for new challenges. However, cloud covers a wide range of concepts with many different perspectives, which can easily dilute and derail discussions preventing a transparent approach to the matter.

Both individuals and organisations need to be aware of the existence of these different perspectives in order to evaluate what the cloud can actually offer them. This awareness is also required to allow organisations to develop strategies as to how to use a mix of public, on premise (or private), community and hybrid cloud solutions in order to provide cost efficient, high quality IT services to their end users. It is this IT/Governance competency of adequately sourcing supply to match a variety of user demand which needs to be developed within organisations.

Specific to the research and education sector, key areas to be identified are:

- where the cloud model is actually feasible (such as generic storage of research data or collaboration between students)
- where it is not (such as data intensive interdependent HPC tasks that require low latency computing)
- the preconditions (including security, interoperability and portability) under which these services may be procured from commercial vendors in the public cloud, or for which applications a more specialised sector cloud approach to allow for bespoke approach is needed.

A critical mass is needed to be reached in order to steer public cloud providers to provide services which allow for an open and free market for cloud providers (both from outside the sector and from within) which does not impose serious risks (in terms of service, privacy and vendor lock in) on consumers (whether that being organisations or individuals).

Various initiatives already exist in the form of national bodies, expert groups and more flexible and non-institutionalised communities, which are addressing some of these issues. However alignment is needed between those initiatives to prevent unnecessary isolated, redundant and divergent development needs. Such an alignment would provide an overarching policy and governance framework to support these activities and enable cross-fertilisation between existing activities. These activities should furthermore be directed to:

- Undertake procurement and national license negotiation between cloud service providers and academia
- Provide template agreements between cloud service providers and academia
- Assist academic run cloud services as regards contractual agreements and service level agreements
- Advocate standards and legal frameworks into the EU
- Benchmark cloud providers as regards trust, reliability, privacy and so on.

For the co-ordination of national bodies governing these aspects, the NREN model for network provision may provide a suitable architecture to base this upon. The coordination bodies and communities can also serve as centres of expertise to the benefit of support within the local organisations with advice and

guidance to develop the aforementioned competences in the short term. This would also provide a conduit for the Research and Academic communities into the proposed European Cloud Partnership³¹. On the other hand, overarching co-ordination at the EU (or global) level could provide a necessary policy framework for delivering the grand auto-scalable federated cloud vision.

A next step would be to instigate the formation of a broadly formulated think tank to investigate the policy structures outlined above. This should run alongside the technological and standards activities already underway within the EU research area, their relationship with existing initiatives including the European Cloud Partnership, and potential governance structures and remit.

³¹ <http://europa.eu/rapid/pressReleasesAction.do?reference=SPEECH/12/38&format=HTML&aged=0&language=EN&guiLanguage=en>

Consortium

IRELAND		Higher Education Authority (HEA)
UNITED KINGDOM		Higher Education Funding Council for England HEFCE (JISC)
NETHERLANDS		SURFfoundation (SURF)
PORTUGAL		Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT)
LATVIA		Latvian Academy of Sciences (LAS)
SPAIN		Ministry of Economy and Competitiveness (MINECO)
FINLAND		CSC - IT Center for Science (CSC)
HUNGARY		National Information Infrastructure Development Institute (NIIFI)
TURKEY		The Scientific and Technological Research Council of Turkey (TUBITAK)
ISRAEL		The Israel-Europe R&D Directorate (ISERD)
GREECE		The General Secretariat for Research and Technology (GSRT)
BELGIUM		Department of Economy, Science and Innovation, Flemish Government (EWI)

Visit the e-InfraNet website:
www.e-infranet.eu

Enhanced Participation:
The current partnership is keen to attract further participation.

Those interested in participating in the project's activities should contact the co-ordinator: Pat O'Connor

e-mail: poconnor@hea.ie